

Studies on a new composite material polyanilinezirconium(IV) tungstophosphate – a thorium(IV) selective cation exchanger

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A new composite ion exchanger polyanilinezirconium(IV) tungstophosphate has been synthesized with the precipitation of zirconium tungstophosphate gel followed by polymerization of aniline in the presence of ammonium persulfate (APS). Its ion exchange capacities, ESCA, TGA, DTA, IR, X-ray, pH titrations, distribution behavior have been reported. Its utility has been explored by achieving the separation of La^{III} from Th^{IV}.

In view of our continued interest in zirconium(IV) tungstophosphate as an active component^{1,2}, the present paper deals with the preparation of composite ion exchange material, its characterization using ESCA, TGA, DTA, X-ray, IR and SEM analysis, ion exchange capacity, chemical dissolution, distribution behavior of twelve metal ions in different systems and its utility by achieving separation of La^{III} from Th^{IV} on its column.

Results and discussion

The synthesized zirconium(IV) tungstophosphate exhibits good ion exchange capacity (Table 1) which varies with the variation in hydrated ionic radius of cations. Ion exchange capacity decreases with the decrease in hydrated ionic radius. Polyaniline zirconium(IV) tungstophosphate shows higher ion exchange capacity than zirconium(IV) tungstophosphate³. The trend indicates that binding polymer exercises synergetic effect towards ion exchange capacity.

Table 1. Ion exchange capacity of polyanilinezirconium(IV) tungstophosphate for different cations

Cation	pH	Hydrated ionic radius (Å)	Ion exchange capacity (meq/g) dry exchanger
Na ⁺	6.7	7.9	1.46
K ⁺	6.8	5.3	0.82
Mg ²⁺	6.5	10.8	2.00
Ca ²⁺	6.5	9.6	1.38
Sr ²⁺	6.5	9.4	0.86
Ba ²⁺	6.5	9.3	0.80

The ESCA analysis provides the % composition of the material as Zr (7.10), O (11.25), C (1.40), N (0.25), W (44.0), P (19.2), H (16.8). Hence, polyaniline zirconium(IV) tungstophosphate contains more anionic component (due to the presence of higher percentage of W and P which con-

stitute tungstophosphate anion), thereby exhibiting better ion exchanger capacity than zirconium(IV) tungstophosphate.

The chemical dissolution in DIW, $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ HNO₃, DMF and in *n*-butanol is almost negligible, thereby showing its fair chemical stability. It may be due to the presence of binding polymer, which prevents the dissolution of heteropolyacid salt or leaching of any constituent elements into the solution.

The infrared spectrum of polyanilinezirconium(IV) tungstophosphate reveals bands at 3600–3300 due to ν_1 (OH), the 3000–2900 and 1630–1600 cm⁻¹ due to deformation vibrations of coordinated water and deformation vibration of interstitial water respectively. The sharp band at 1500 cm⁻¹ is due to bending of N–H bonds. The bands at 1320, 1300 and 1250 cm⁻¹ are due to superposition of metal-oxygen stretching vibrations and at 1080–1020, 960 and 880 cm⁻¹ due to superposition of metal substituent sensitive vibrations in benzene ring [ν_2 (W–O, Zr–O and P–O)] and aqua wagging twisting and rocking modes. The infrared studies support the presence of aniline in this composite ion exchange material.

Table 2. Distribution coefficients (ml/g) of metal ions on polyanilinezirconium(IV) tungstophosphate

Metal ion	DIW	pH 3 ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) HNO ₃	DMF	<i>n</i> -Butanol
Mg ²⁺	32.6	37.3	86.9	322
Ca ²⁺	3.0	29.3	135	605
Sr ²⁺	4.0	1.0	30	119.1
Ba ²⁺	3.8	10.1	67.7	616
Zn ²⁺	7.2	18.2	63.4	374
Cd ²⁺	10.6	23	23	102
Hg ²⁺	69.4	54	146	146
Pb ²⁺	86.5	97.80	97.8	308.5
Ni ²⁺	17.2	17.2	17.2	108
Th ⁴⁺	1966.7	1140	313.3	113.8
La ³⁺	163.3	140	29.5	1.2
UO ₂ ²⁺	122.0	264	122	115

Table 3. Separation of La^{III} from Th^{IV}

Sl. no.	Mixture	Amount loaded μg	Amount found μg	Metal ions eluted %	Error %	Total elution volume (ml)	Eluent used ^a
1.	La ^{III}	860	882	102.25	+2.55	30	A
	Th ^{IV}	928	906	97.63	-2.37	40	B
2.	La ^{III}	1540	1448	94.02	-5.98	50	A
	Th ^{IV}	1630	1686	103.43	+3.43	50	B
3.	La ^{III}	2320	2208	95.17	-4.83	70	A
	Th ^{IV}	2380	1905	91.58	+8.42	90	B

^a A = 1.0×10^{-5} M HNO₃; B = glacial acetic acid + *n*-butanol (1 : 1).

The thermogram of polyanilinezirconium(IV) tungstophosphate that there is only 2.5% loss at 40–100^o, which may be attributed due to the presence of gel water adhered to the material. The further loss of 6.5% at 100–200^o is due to loss of water of crystallization. The loss of 7.0% at 200–400^o may be attributed to the loss of coordinated water condensation of hydroxy groups and the oxidation of polyaniline. The loss of 7.0% at 400–600^o is due to the conversion of phosphate and tungstates into their corresponding oxides and the change in oxidation products of polyaniline. Finally, the loss of 8.0% at 600–800^o is due to various changes in the oxides of zirconium, tungsten and phosphorus.

Differential thermal analysis shows the continuous endothermic changes from 250 to 270^o. This change confirms the changes recorded in thermogram of the material and this composite change is designated to the sum of all attributions within this temperature range. The small peak at 840–920^o may be due to the phase transition taking place within oxides of zirconium, tungsten and phosphorus.

X-Ray diffraction pattern shows a number of peaks at different 2θ values. The analysis of these signal peaks support towards its crystalline nature. Scanning electron microphotographs obtained at the magnifications of 160, 1250 and 2500 reveal its crystalline regions. The SEM photograph (magnification 160) does not exhibit the two regions of crystalline and of amorphous character but as the magnification increases these two regions becoming quite visible. SEM photograph (magnification 2500) clearly indicates the binding of ion exchange material by organic polymer, i.e. polyaniline. The detail analysis of these SEM photographs informs that its particle size may be about 2.8 μm.

pH titrations with NaCl-NaOH system suggest that this composite ion exchange material is polyfunctional in character. The distribution behavior of 12 metal ions have been observed and the distribution coefficients (K_d) values are shown in Table 2, which show the preferential uptake of

Th^{IV} in DIW, 1.0×10^{-3} M HNO₃ and DMF while its uptake declines in *n*-butanol system. The K_d values for other metal ions have almost the similar trend in DIW, 1.0×10^{-3} M HNO₃ and DMF systems. In *n*-butanol system, the uptake of all metal ions almost shifts to new trend that may be due to the change in polarity of the system in which almost all-bivalent metal ions show higher K_d values.

The separation factors involving Th^{IV} and UO₂^{II} ions with others were studied. The most interesting separation is that of La^{III} from Th^{IV} ions (Table 3). The separations carry percent error in their recovery from ±1.8 to 9.3.

Experimental

Zirconium oxychloride (Aldrich), sodium tungstate, ammonium sodium hydrogen orthophosphate, aniline and ammonium persulfate (all C.D.H., A.R.) were employed for the synthesis of polyaniline zirconium(IV) tungstophosphate. Century CP901 pH meter, Shimadzu IR 435 spectrophotometer, 750 Shimadzu ESCA, Dupont 9900 (with 951 module) TGA, Stanton red craft STA (with 781 module) DTA, PW 1130 Philips X-Ray, Philips 50 and 360 Cambridge SEM and GS5700 ECIL spectrophotometer were used.

Polyaniline zirconium(IV) tungstophosphate : Zirconium(IV) tungstophosphate (ZWP) was synthesized by reported method³. To ZWP, aniline (400 ml) was added and the solution allowed to cool to 0–5^o. Acting as a catalyst, ammonium persulfate (80 g) was finally added to the solution and set aside overnight. The resulting green colored gel was washed with 1 M HCl, deionized water (DIW) and diethyl ether, and dried at 50 ± 2^o. The gel was converted into granules by adding DIW and then converted into H⁺-form by placing in 3 M HNO₃ for 2–3 days. The excess of acid was washed with DIW and again dried at 50 ± 2^o.

Ion exchange capacity of polyanilinezirconium(IV) tungstophosphate (PaZWP in H⁺-form) was studied. The pH titrations of the polyanilinezirconium(IV) tungstophos-

phate were performed by reported method⁴ for NaCl-NaOH systems. The chemical composition of polyanilinezirconium(IV) tungstophosphate was determined by the ESCA (electron spectrometer for chemical analysis). The chemical dissolution of polyanilinezirconium(IV) tungstophosphate was carried out in DIW, $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ HNO₃, DMF and *n*-butanol. The presence of zirconium, tungsten and phosphorus were tested spectrophotometrically⁵. TGA of polyanilinezirconium(IV) tungstophosphate in H⁺-form was carried out at the rate of 10^o/min and DTA at a rate of 10^o/min under nitrogen environment taking alumina as reference. SEM photographs were taken at 160, 1250 and 2500 magnifications. Distribution coefficient (K_d) was determined by the usual method⁶ and separation factor (α^A) for the metal ions was calculated. Quantitative separation of metal ions was achieved on a glass column (0.6 cm i.e.) using the exchanger (1000–120 mesh size; 1.0 g) in H⁺-form. A metal ion mixture was poured on the top of the column and the flow rate of the eluent was maintained at 14–16 drops/min throughout.

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